

EVALUATION OF SAFETY SYSTEM IN EGYPTIAN INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECTS BASED ON LEVEL OF INJURIES

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Abstract- The construction industry is pivotal in developing global infrastructure and economic expansion. Nevertheless, it is infamous for its high accident rates and safety concerns. Despite accounting for only 7 % of global employment, construction is responsible for approximately 30 % of all fatal workplace fatalities worldwide. In developing countries, the situation is even worse. The injury itself can vary from case to case, starting from small injuries that require first aid treatment to severe injuries that can cause long-term disabilities and, ultimately, death. From a safety and health perspective, the absence of implementing the safety system on site causes many accidents that could lead to death or disability. In this work safety absence management factors of Egyptian infrastructure projects are collected using questionnaire. This paper aims to study the relation between the absence of safety factor in infrastructure sites and the level of injury by using statistical analysis for collected data from construction projects partners. The questionnaire answer analyzed by using SPSS program and PCA method (principal component analysis) which reached to identify 41 models to identify the level of injury. The result of model function identifies the level of injury which more close to 1 the level of injury decrease which mean superficial or minor injury. The interested companies could choose the suitable model due to its type of infrastructure projects and safety system. The researcher explained the model no (15) equation and model variable as an example.

Keywords- Construction industry, Workplace safety, Occupational health, Accident rates, Injury severity, Safety management.

I. INTRODUCTION

according to research (Shukra et al., 2021). Few researches explain the term infrastructure more closely to the projects which unseen or underground projects, other type of researches gives a possible classification of infrastructure as its effect on economic, physical and social life. Low situational awareness contributes to safety incidents in construction (Chen et al., 2024). The accident significant increase in the complexity and diversity of

behavior-based on hazards on construction sites also led the research and practitioner community to seek more effective safety behavior interventions (Yan et al., 2022). In Finland, 178 occupational accidents the unsafe behavior of workers accounts for 84–94% of incidents due to skill-based, rule-based, and knowledge-based human errors. Any act or behavior that deviates from safety instructions and standards, such as unsafe use of the equipment or not wearing Personal Protective Equipment (PPE), poses major risks not only to the workers but also to any people in the vicinity of hazards. Additionally,

the vast majority of safety surveillance mechanisms that have been in use are no longer efficient and cost-effective (Cheng, Luo, et al., 2022). Ensuring worker safety is an essential aspect of construction management. Despite the provision of safety measures, statistics reveal that unsafe practices persist (Waqar et al., 2024) A lot of researchers evaluate the success of infrastructure projects as a critical element in achieving life facilities as desirable flexibility and quality of life, achieving economic growth, civilized development and technological change.

Between 2009 and 2019, China recorded an average of 2851 fatalities per annum due to non-compliance with safety regulations (Chenet al., 2024) from (MHURDC). For instance, the Australian construction sector reported 183 fatal injuries from 2017 to 2021, which highlights the severity of the issue (Australia, 2016). Oxford Business Group, 2017, In Egypt, recorded that the construction sector ranked the third after the tourism and communications sectors in 2017 in the contribution towards the Egyptian economy. The construction sector increased by 10.3% compared to the preceding year which recorded as an output of the construction industry to the Egyptian economy in 2016, Fig.1

Fig. 1: The growth of global construction industry

from 2014 to 2025 (Oxford Business Group, 2017)

II. SAMPLE SIZE

The responsibility for infrastructure projects in Egypt depends on many sectors, including the public sector, the private sector, and the business sector of types, the public business sector and the private business sector. Central Agency for Public Mobilization and Statistics, 2022 mention that the

public sector for construction has about 107000 workers in construction field, this number for public sector only. Added to that Unregistered and migrant workers. So the questionnaire sample depending on unlimited population.

The questionnaire was distributed as a hard copy and a Google form which collected 250 responses to assess either the reliability and validity of the questionnaire to prepare the internal structural and consistency validity tests. As the researcher ensured the reliability and validity of the questionnaire used, all 600 questionnaires

$$n = \frac{n_0 * M}{n_0 + M - 1} = 384$$

Where: : initial sample size = 384

M : the variance of the population of size

: suggested calculated sample size.

III. QUESTIONNAIRE DATA COLLECTION

The questionnaire element in this research was based on the literature review which was based on textbooks, academic and professional journals, safety and health conferences, theses, organizations and government publications, as well as internet and related websites as (Umar, 2019, Nawaz, etal, 2020). The questionnaire was composed of eight sections to accomplish the aim of this research, as follows:

1. Some information about the participant and his company and the executed projects as number accident in projects and effect of safety in project cost and time as control variables.
2. Integrating the value of safety through set of questions discusses the scope to which construction institutions accept the idea of achieving security and safety as a value before starting implementation work and educating those in charge of work.
3. This part of the questionnaire includes the organization's orientations towards the development of the safety system, the extent to which the development can be implemented.

4. Studying the role of the institution in encouraging and involving workers to adhere to safety requirements
5. Discussing if the institution capable of activating the role of participation and communication among its members towards implementing safety.
6. This part includes institution role in developing its safety system for all levels of its employees.
7. Measuring if the institution taking responsibility for the worker at the site.
8. Identifying the acceptance of the client or the owner of the idea of applying safety during implementation.

The questionnaire was prepared in more than one way to distribute it, which including both internet questionnaire and paper questionnaire. To complete and meaningful response of the questionnaire an interview was conducted with some respondent to explain the objective of the study and to discuss input towards the questionnaire design, especially towards identifying safety and safety management actions for controlling the site accident. Some of the questionnaires were filled throughout the interview. The questionnaire is depending on evaluate the element by the degree of its existence in infrastructure projects site by using strongly disagree, disagree, normal, agree and strongly agree. The element could be simple questions or explanatory sentences, as:

1-Participant information and working company
Age, carrier, education and If accident happened, level of injury

2-Aligning Safety and Integrating It as Value

- Defining safety expectation in the organization as policies, Procedures and communication
- Construction worker safety was already an important issue for designers to take care of it
- Defining safety as most important topic in all organization meeting.
- Insinuating designers to information about how they affect safety on a construction project is important.
- Leadership supports the safety as value.
- Defining safety roles and member's responsibilities at all organization levels.
- Effectively provide adequate resources Implementation of safety activities.

- In your organization, Training support safety as value for supervisors and workers.
- Identifying clearly safety expectations in policies, procedures, and guidelines.
- The management's vision reflects the monitoring of workers and safety behaviors at the site.
- In your organization, providing sufficient safety training.
- Conducting external safety assessments in the organization.
- Take corrective action early.
- Identifying clearly safety expectations in policies, procedures, and guidelines.
- Encourage workers to actively participate in safety implementation by designing rewards.
- Sharing safety responsibility between all project members.
- Management commitment towards safety has high effect on the safety climate on construction organizations.
- Promote a communication culture on the topic of safety in the organization through leadership alters, newsletters and leadership letters.

• **Improve safety performance in the construction industry**

- Merging safety during planning process.
- In your organization, defining safety roles and responsibilities clearly at all levels.
- Sharing major leader in safety issues.
- Ensuring supervisors lead by example.
- Hold workers responsible for their safety.
- Strengthen learning environment depending on leadership.
- Promoting safety training to supervisors in communication, motivation, and preplanning.
- Involving workers through site orientations to participate in safety implementation.
- Establishing a common working management.
- Workers involvement in job risk analysis.
- Conduct Joint tours regularly to specify specific problems raised by workers.
- Workers are often asked to participate perception about safety implementation.
- Encouraging workers to report potential risks and injuries.

- Ensuring workers feel empowered implementation authority.
- **Encouraging and involving workers**
 - Encouraging workers on site orientations to actively participate in safety execution.
 - Customizing worker-management safety committee.
 - Involvement of workers in job risk analyses.
 - Studying specific problems raised by workers on site.
 - Sharing workers perceptions about safety implementation over and over.
 - Encouraging workers to report potential injuries in the time.
 - Ensuring that workers feel empowered with stop-work authority
 - Providing safety training at all workers specification and supervisors.
 - Encouraging supervisors to have certification in safety and health.
 - Providing prevention through design training engineers.
 - Encouraging all field workers to give their needs explanation in training.
- **Effect of communication on safety**
 - Policies and procedures explanation so that all workers understand them.
 - Considering safety as constant item in every meeting agenda.
 - Identifying leaders who help communicate safety messages.
 - Defining system for sharing information.
 - Applying transparent process to address employee safety concerns.
 - Supervisors and management provide timely feedback on safety reports.
 - Applying mentoring safety to workers.
- **Training Efficiency**
 - Ensuring that all level of the organization having safety training.
 - Encouraging managers and leadership to have certification in safety and health.
 - Providing prevention through design training to engineers.
- Encouraging all field workers to identify training needs and developing materials.
- Defining safety committee training to all participants
- Providing safety training at all levels of the organization.
- **Measuring responsibility on the organization**
 - Identifying a fair system
 - For all project partners, defining safety expectations in policies, procedures, and guidelines, and communicating consistently across the organization.
 - Adopting safety insurance program controlled by owner.
 - Enforcing safety policies and procedures for all project level.
 - Submitting promoting and rewarding incentive structures for safety processes.
 - Conducting evaluating safety performance system.
 - Evaluating safety experience during hiring of managers and subcontractors.
 - Distributing safety activities to all members of the project team.
- **Encouraging Owner / Client Involvement**
 - Improve safety performance by developing guidelines in construction industry.
 - Devoting adequate resources to safety implementation by owners.
 - Participation of owners in employee's orientation meeting and daily planning.
 - Owners visit employees regularly to connect with them and learn from their safety problems.
 - Presence of owner representative on-site to monitor and assist with safety implementation.
 - Building information modeling in design and planning phases by owners.
 - Prequalification of bids due to safety performance by owners.
 - Reviewing and supporting safety performance by owners.
 - Ensure that workers don't get retaliated by owners to raise safety concerns.
 - In Owner controlled insurance programs, giving workers a financial share for maintaining safety.

- Improve safety performance by developing guidelines in construction industry.
- Devoting adequate resources to safety implementation by owners.
- Participation of owners in employee's orientation meeting and daily planning.

IV. DESCRIPTIVE APPROACH ADVANTAGES

Using the descriptive approach in this study has many advantages can be summarized as:

- Display all the information about important factors that can be behind accident in Egyptian construction sites through the researching process and introduces a clear detailed description of the scientific manual employed through the descriptive analysis process.
- Introduces an accurate causal forecasting for the future to the effect of the accident in Egyptian construction sites on cost overrun and time delay of infrastructure projects in Egypt.
- Empowers the capability to collect more accurate and relevant data about the studied variables, as improving safety performance in the construction industry.
- It can easily describe the relationship among the various phenomena and variables, also investigates all the differences or similarities among the problems study.
- The approach is fully complied with specific nature, of this study as it can clarify the nature of the relationship between the basic information as a control variable, and Level of injury from the accident as dependent variable, and integrating safety as a value , Improving safety performance in the construction industry, Encouraging and engaging workers, Impact of communication on safety, Training efficiency, Measuring the responsibility of the organization, and Encourage owner/customer participation as independent variables to predict how to employ findings of the results obtained in the future researches, or in the practical life of the practitioners.

V. STATISTICAL PACKAGE FOR THE SOCIAL SCIENCES (SPSS)

The data was displayed in tables and figures to give a clear picture of the discoveries at hand, then quantitatively examined from top to bottom using the statistical package for social scientists (SPSS) computer programming package due to its relative accuracy, speed and relevancy to the variables studied and the specific nature of the relationship between the variables.

VI. DATA ANALYSIS

The questionnaire has 600 responded, 250 from the internet one and 350 from the paper. The questionnaire was distributed to different categories in terms of gender (male or female), the age, education degree, type of institution and experience in work.

Control Variables

Distribution of the study sample members was:

- Based on the gender 77.8 % male and 22.3 % female.
- Based on the age less than 31 39.8% , from 31 to 40 is 44.2% , from 41 to 50 is 11.8%, from 51 to 70 is 2.7.2% and more than 60 is 1.5%
- According to the Job level are manager 28%, Manager 49%, chief worker 7%, General Worker 5% and other job 5%
- According to years of experience there are 194 members has 6 – 10 years' experience which represents about 32.3% of the sample, and there are 92 members has 11 – 16 years' experience which represents about 15.3% of the sample, and finally, there are 49 members has 16 -20 years' experience which represents about 8.2% of the selected sample, the analysis reveals that the majority of the sample (72.6%) hold a less than 11 years of experience
- there are 502 members in the selected sample have a bachelor degree, which represents about 83.7% of the sample
- according to organization construction work type, Table. 1

Table. 1: Distribution of the study sample members according to organization construction work type

Organization Construction Work type	Responses	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
road work	232	38.7	38.7	38.7
utility work	220	36.6	36.6	75.3
irrigation facilities	46	7.7	7.7	83.0
tunnel work	12	2.0	2.0	85.0
Any other	90	15.0	15.0	100.0
Total	600	100	100	

Table. 2: Distribution of the study sample members according to organization classification

Organization classification	Responses	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
Owner	114	19.0	19.0	19.0

Contractor	312	52.0	52.0	71.0
Subcontractor	54	9.0	9.0	80.0
consultant	120	20.0	20.0	100.0
Total	600	100	100	

- According to the level of injury which considered the result to safety absence in Egyptian infrastructure project sites. About 32.3% of questionnaire respondent was injured or an injury occurred while they were present at the site and it is a non-neglected percentage, table 3. The distribution of injury percent is classified in fig 2. Fire forms 13.91%, electric injuries (Short circuit & Exposure to electric current) form 9.27%, and misuse of protective devices (Penetration of a solid object into protective devices & not wearing full protective gear) form 5.67%, this can show risk sources to be avoided for a safety environment.

Table: 3 Distribution of the study sample members according to level of injury.

level of injury	Responses	%	Valid %	Cumulative %
No injury	406	67.7	67.7	67.7
Superficial injury	108	18.0	18.0	85.7

Moderate injury	62	10.3	10.3	96
Major injury (disability or death)	24	4.0	4.0	100.0
Total	600	100	100	

Fig 2 Distribution of the study sample members according to reasons of injuries.

Descriptive analysis

To recognize respondents' answers about the different parts of the survey as Value the researcher made a descriptive analysis to their answers

- Align and integrate safety as a value, construction worker safety was already an important issue for designers to take care of it was the most important statement in aligning safety and integrating it as value, but conducting external safety assessments in the organization was the least important statement.
- Improve safety performance in the construction industry, encouraging workers to report potential risks and injuries was the most important statement in improve safety performance in the construction industry but hold workers responsible for their safety was the least important statement.
- Encouraging and involving workers, encouraging workers to report potential injuries in the time was the most important statement. Ensuring that workers feel empowered with

stop-work authority was the least important statement.

- Effect of communication on safety, applying mentoring safety to workers was the most important statement in effect of communication on safety but identifying leaders who help communicate safety messages was the least important statement.
- Tanning efficiency, ensuring that all level of the organization having safety training was the most important statement in training efficiency but defining safety committee training to all participants was the least important statement.
- Measuring the responsibility of organization, conducting evaluating safety performance system was the most important statement in measuring responsibility on the organization but adopting safety insurance program controlled by owner was the least important statement.
- Encouraging owner / client involvement, ensure that workers don't retaliated by owners to raise safety concerns. Was the most important statement in Encouraging Owner / Client Involvement but Improve safety performance by developing guidelines in construction industry was the least important statement.

VII. RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN VARIABLES

Studying is there any relationship between dependent variables; the next table can give an answer.

Table: 4 Relationships (Spearman's Correlation) between study variables

	the level of injury	Aligning Safety and Integrating It as Value	improve Safety Performance in the Construction Industry	Encouraging and Involving Workers	Effect of communication on safety	Training Efficiency	Measuring responsibility on the organization	Encouraging Owner / Client Involvement
the level of injury	1.000	-.167*	-.279**	-.250**	-.241**	-.204**	-.319**	-.166*
Aligning Safety and Integrating It as Value	-.167*	1.000	.789**	.822**	.749**	.697**	.746**	.703**
improve Safety Performance in the Construction Industry	-.279**	.789**	1.000	.834**	.712**	.616**	.696**	.602**
Encouraging and Involving Workers	-.250**	.822**	.834**	1.000	.836**	.739**	.783**	.668**
Effect of communication on safety	-.241**	.749**	.712**	.836**	1.000	.800**	.798**	.664**
Training Efficiency	-.204**	.697**	.616**	.739**	.800**	1.000	.786**	.717**
Measuring responsibility on the organization	-.319**	.746**	.696**	.783**	.798**	.786**	1.000	.741**
Encouraging Owner / Client Involvement	-.166*	.703**	.602**	.668**	.664**	.717**	.741**	1.000

All dependent variables correlated each other's with a positive and high relation and p.values are less than 0.01. Where:

- * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)
- ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

VIII. ANOVA TABLE FOR DEPENDENT VARIABLE (LEVEL OF INJURY)

Using communalities analysis, which are the proportion of variance in a variable that is explained by the underlying factors, which means, it is the amount of variance in a variable that is shared with other variables in the dataset and variables with high communality value indicates that they are well represented by the underlying factors and can be used in the factor analysis. Conversely, a variable with a low communality value indicates that it is not well represented by the underlying factors and should be removed from the analysis; the table below shows all variable communalities.

The communalities show with Principal Component Analysis as the extraction Method used that if we make a regression model for estimating the level of injury it can explain 87% of the variance of level of injury.

IX. TOTAL VARIANCE EXPLAINED

Factor analysis explains a lot of models using Total Variance Explained and eigenvalues for each variable; the table below shows all variable Eigenvalues and Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings.

The next table shows the eigenvalues of each factor and the percentage of variance explained by each factor, where, The last row of the table shows the total variance explained by all the factors together which is 100% for this data whereas in component (32) there are about 99.993% total variance explained which is the sum of the variances of all the factors extracted, and It is a measure of the total amount of variance in the observed variables that is accounted for by the factors shown in table 5 is the output of the factor analysis, we can notice 14 component can explained 90.8% from the total amount of variance in the observed variables.

Table 5 factors` Eigenvalues and Loadings

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	37.412	49.227	49.227	37.412	49.227	49.227
2	6.003	7.899	57.126	6.003	7.899	57.126
3	3.779	4.973	62.099	3.779	4.973	62.099
4	3.677	4.838	66.937	3.677	4.838	66.937
5	2.790	3.671	70.608	2.790	3.671	70.608
6	2.421	3.186	73.794	2.421	3.186	73.794
7	2.177	2.865	76.658	2.177	2.865	76.658
8	1.949	2.564	79.222	1.949	2.564	79.222
9	1.816	2.390	81.612	1.816	2.390	81.612
10	1.656	2.179	83.791	1.656	2.179	83.791
11	1.609	2.117	85.909	1.609	2.117	85.909
12	1.516	1.994	87.903	1.516	1.994	87.903
13	1.135	1.493	89.396	1.135	1.493	89.396
14	1.074	1.413	90.809	1.074	1.413	90.809
32	0.029	0.038	99.993			

X. REGRESSION MODEL FOR LEVEL OF INJURY

factor analysis for the study's data explained that the data is fitting the regression model, researcher made a regression model to estimate the level of injury in SPSS, results as in the below table 6.

Table: 6 Regression models R2 and Std. Error of the Estimate

Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Model	R	R-Square	Adjusted R-Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.414	0.171	0.167	0.64248	22	0.987	0.974	0.971	0.12003
2	0.584	0.341	0.334	0.57439	23	0.995	0.990	0.988	0.07604
3	0.65	0.423	0.414	0.53884	24	0.997	0.994	0.993	0.05693
4	0.689	0.475	0.464	0.51557	25	0.998	0.996	0.996	0.04682
5	0.737	0.543	0.531	0.48192	26	0.999	0.997	0.997	0.03884
6	0.754	0.568	0.554	0.46987	27	0.999	0.997	0.997	0.03883
7	0.786	0.617	0.603	0.44358	28	0.999	0.999	0.999	0.02609
8	0.827	0.683	0.670	0.40461	29	1.000	0.999	0.999	0.02356
9	0.827	0.683	0.671	0.40364	30	1.000	0.999	0.999	0.02026
10	0.847	0.717	0.705	0.38230	31	1.000	1.000	0.999	0.01608
11	0.862	0.744	0.731	0.36494	32	1.000	1.000	0.999	0.01608
12	0.873	0.763	0.750	0.35196	33	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.01100
13	0.889	0.790	0.777	0.33207	34	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00929
14	0.899	0.808	0.795	0.31871	35	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00676
15	0.911	0.831	0.818	0.29993	36	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00496
16	0.923	0.852	0.840	0.28143	37	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00036
17	0.937	0.879	0.869	0.25517	38	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00036
18	0.952	0.907	0.898	0.22448	39	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00001
19	0.961	0.924	0.916	0.20384	40	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00000
20	0.972	0.946	0.940	0.17251	41	1.000	1.000	1.000	0.00000
21	0.982	0.965	0.961	0.13934					

Table: 8 shows variables coefficients for regression model no 15

Variable	Unstandardized B	Unstandardized Std. error	Standardized B	T	Sig.
(Constant)	1.773	0.223		7.938	0.000
Identifying a fair system	-0.509	0.049	-0.526	-10.413	0.000
In Owner controlled insurance programs, giving workers a financial share for maintaining safety.	0.518	0.042	0.592	12.400	0.000
Submitting promoting and rewarding	0.573	0.077	0.582	7.470	0.000
Devoting adequate resources to safety implementation by owners.	0.570	0.049	0.600	11.647	0.000
Merging safety during planning process.	-0.516	0.047	-0.688	-11.090	0.000
Encouraging all field workers to identify training needs and developing materials.	-0.938	0.074	-0.813	-12.638	0.000
Establishing a common working management.	0.804	0.057	0.905	14.209	0.000
Workers are often asked to participate perception about safety implementation.	-0.717	0.059	-0.910	-12.222	0.000
Take corrective action early.	0.489	0.043	0.609	11.438	0.000
Hold workers responsible for their safety.	-0.142	0.026	-0.203	-5.506	0.000
Effectively provide adequate resources Implementation of safety activities.	-0.266	0.043	-0.369	-6.139	0.000
Encouraging workers to report potential risks and injuries	0.331	0.054	0.439	6.181	0.000
Studying specific problems raised by workers on site.	-0.277	0.056	-0.310	-4.938	0.000

XII. MODELS VARIABLES

Each accepted model has its variables and each variable in any model has its coefficient to show how it works researcher make model with coefficient of determination (R^2 :0.818) in the table above. The above table shows that we can estimate level of injury by using data from (13) variables which are:

- ν : Identifying a fair system (-0.509)
- ω : In owner-controlled insurance programs, giving workers a financial share for maintaining safety (0.518).
- δ : Submitting promoting and rewarding (0.573)
- ϵ : Devoting adequate resources to safety implementation by owners. (0.570)
- I : Merging safety during planning process. (- 0.516)
- ϕ : Encouraging all field workers to identify training needs and developing materials. (- 0.938)
- z : Establishing a common working management. (0.804)
- z : Workers are often asked to participate perception about safety implementation. (- 0.717)
- w : Take corrective action early. (0.489)
- h : Hold workers responsible for their safety. (- 0.142)
- Ψ : Effectively provide adequate resources Implementation of safety activities. (-0.266)

Table 8 ANOVA table for regression models

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	16.38	1	16.38	39.67	0.000	22	93.14	20	4.66	323.24	0.000
2	32.61	2	16.31	49.43	0.000	23	94.63	21	4.51	779.42	0.000
3	40.46	3	13.49	46.45	0.000	24	95.07	22	4.32	1333.35	0.000
4	45.39	4	11.35	42.69	0.000	25	95.26	23	4.14	1889.12	0.000
5	51.97	5	10.39	44.75	0.000	26	95.37	24	3.97	2634.27	0.000
6	54.34	6	9.06	41.02	0.000	27	95.37	23	4.15	2750.25	0.000
7	59.03	7	8.43	42.86	0.000	28	95.51	24	3.98	5845.10	0.000
8	65.34	8	8.17	49.89	0.000	29	95.54	25	3.82	6884.43	0.000
9	65.32	7	9.33	57.28	0.000	30	95.56	26	3.68	8950.68	0.000
10	68.59	8	8.57	58.67	0.000	31	95.59	27	3.54	13683.83	0.000
11	71.12	9	7.90	59.34	0.000	32	95.59	26	3.68	14225.73	0.000
12	72.96	10	7.30	58.90	0.000	33	95.61	27	3.54	29264.60	0.000
13	75.56	11	6.87	62.29	0.000	34	95.61	28	3.41	39557.41	0.000
14	77.24	12	6.44	63.37	0.000	35	95.62	29	3.30	72153.31	0.000
15	79.44	13	6.11	67.93	0.000	36	95.62	30	3.19	129676.66	0.000
16	81.45	14	5.82	73.45	0.000	37	95.63	31	3.08	23472858.19	0.000
17	84.04	15	5.60	86.04	0.000	38	95.63	30	3.19	24197624.91	0.000
18	86.71	16	5.42	107.54	0.000	39	95.63	31	3.08	28552294698.53	0.000
19	88.32	17	5.20	125.03	0.000	40	95.63	32	2.99		
20	90.42	18	5.02	168.80	0.000	41	95.63	33	2.90		
21	92.25	19	4.86	250.08	0.000						

XI. ACCEPTED MODELS

We can accept or reject any model by its significant that less than 0.05 which means all are accepted. Each accepted model has its variables and each variable in any model has its coefficient to show how it works. By choose model no (15) with coefficient of determination (R^2 :0.818) and standard Error of the estimate which reached (0.29993) to concentrate on the most effective variables. Table 7 shows variables coefficients for regression models.

- Q: Encouraging workers to report potential risks and injuries (0.331)
- q: Studying specific problems raised by workers on site (-0.277)
- constant =(1.773)

XIII. MODELS` FUNCTIONS

From Each variable coefficient to for any model we can draw the model function as shown below using model no (15) :

level of injury (L) =

$$1.773 - 0.509 * (\psi) + 0.518 * (\omega) + 0.573 * (\delta) + 0.57 * (\epsilon) - 0.516 * (\lambda) - 0.938 * (\phi) + 0.804 * (\eta) - 0.717 * (z) + 0.489 * (w) - 0.142 * (h) - 0.266 * (\rho) + 0.331 * (Q) - 0.277 * (q) \quad (2)$$

To indicate the safety level in any construction company we can applicate the next equation

$$\text{Safety level (SL)} = 1 - \text{level of injury (L)} \quad (3)$$

XIV. CASE STUDIES

The equation efficiency was applied to measure the level of injury in institutions and its impact on safety application level. The test was conducted on two vital infrastructure institutions, the first one is owner represented in Potable and waste water company in Damietta and the other one is a contractor represented in Military Production Company for Engineering Projects and Consultations. The results were as follows:

- For owner "Potable and waste water company in Damietta", The level of injury due to model equation results was 0.25. That's indicates that safety level about 0.75 and the safety system in the projects under owner institution is operating at approximately 75%. Owner should keep going in developing safety application and trying to avoid deficiencies.
- For contractor "Military Production Company for Engineering Projects", The level of injury due to model equation results was 0.36. That's indicates that safety level about 0.64 and the safety system in the projects executed by contractor is

approximately 64%, this ratio is considered sensitive because it is close to the middle. The contractor must carefully review the safety system during project implementation and re-establish controls to reduce injuries.

XV. CONCLUSION

The title "level of lab on injury prediction in infrastructure projects in Egypt" explains the main purpose of this research, by introducing some factors which affecting workers level of injury due to safety absence in Egyptian infrastructure projects sites. The data collected and presented in questionnaire which introduced to 600 participants working in infrastructure projects field as workers, engineers, supervisors and consultants. The research aims to help institutions responsible for infrastructure projects evaluate their security and safety system by linking it to the degree of accidents. All models are accepted, each accepted model has its variables and each variable in any model has its coefficient to show how it works. From each variable coefficient for any model we can draw the model function. The application of model equation provides an approximate indicator of the safety system in institutions, also facilitating a simplified monitoring of security and safety in infrastructure projects.

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